

Provided on behalf of the Center for Data to Health leadership team:

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Category	Topic	Response (Each topic response limited to 250 words)
Barriers and solutions to improve use of basic research findings to inform clinical care	Identifying critical infrastructure investments essential to strengthening the process of translational science	<p>One major challenge in using basic research to inform clinical care is a fundamental lack of interoperability between terminologies and data models used in different domains. Very few basic research resources are interoperable with clinical ones, and very few people combine these data. Not much NIH funding goes to support terminology standards in any capacity. Issues abound: some of the clinical terminologies are not only not interoperable, they are not open for reuse and redistribution, severely limiting translational informatics applications. Some intramural work on terminologies exists, but it does not include the community very much in its development, again limiting translational impact. Because most standards efforts are grossly underfunded and don't have good sustainability, they do not have any extra bandwidth to go beyond their primary communities that they serve and therefore create the translational interoperability that we need. CTSA's would do well to start having a "standards" expert/concierge service to help all the translational teams that the CTSA's serve. We need to train more people in the application and development of standards so that they can start generating data that is more born-interoperable across our translational divides.</p> <p>We also need to improve Hub websites to share information/resources in a more consistent and discoverable manner. In the consumer world, Google search engine and the corresponding schema.org-based SEO (search engine optimization) techniques have essentially solved the issue for harvesting structured data from distributed and vastly heterogenous web resources. Adopting this tech-stack with the biomedical-specific standardization efforts above can lead to a set of best-practice guides and cloud infrastructure/utilities benefitting both data-sharing (for data-providers) and data-discovery (for data-consumers) in the biomedical research community.</p>
	Developing successful models of multidisciplinary collaboration and team science with effective dissemination to the community	<p>The CTSA hubs could do better to support basic researchers in translational science by providing them improved access and training in using clinical data and helping them identify new collaborations. It seems that for the most part, basic science researchers come to the CTSA looking for clinical evidence to validate or develop a mechanistic hypothesis. However, often the kinds of questions that they have of clinical data are not readily answered by the standardized queries that most research data warehouses and analysts can provide. There are few user interfaces that allow generic exploration, especially with combined basic and clinical data. Finally, there are not many concierge services to hand hold such investigations. The translational collaboration within CTSA hubs seems largely a one way street - basic science researchers are requested to investigate a biological mechanisms based on a clinical question or finding, but CTSA's do little to support the reverse in terms of training and data access.</p>
	Encouraging shared investments with public and private funders, both non-profit and for-profit	<p>Shared investments begin with communication and shared experiences. As described below, we need to build the pipe towards these ends by improving the knowledge transfer across sectors.</p>
	Utilizing an NCATS-provided cloud collaboration environment	<p>Translational research, by its nature, covers a broad spectrum from basic to clinical science. CTSA's need to include in the core processes explicit translation efforts like those being piloted in the NCATS Translator. Cloud infrastructure by its nature is designed to meet the need of "X as a service"-type of applications. Traditionally the research field focuses on the end-user-facing product development, while cloud-focused architecture makes possible to deploy more "intermediate-modules" as a service applications. These "intermediate-modules" are referring to the modular functionalities reusable among multiple end-user-facing products, e.g. schema-as-a-service, identifier-normalization-as-a-service, terminology-as-a-service, knowledge-API-as-a-service (which is being implemented in Translator program) etc. Implementation of secure cloud partitions for CTSA clinical data can support cross-CTSA research analytics. An alternative is bringing tools and algorithms to the data via the cloud, where a data model adaptor can live behind the clinical firewall but talk to the NCATS cloud. The successful implementation of these broad-scope of cloud-services can lead to a healthy, self-evolving, standard-compliant application development ecosystem. Together with the existing end-user-facing applications, such a cloud-driven ecosystem benefits data-exchange and collaboration across hubs and broader research community.</p>
Workforce development	Developing and assessing training efforts to strengthen clinical and translational science	<p>Translational science is a team sport, with a range of roles and expertise needed across the full "translational spectrum" to maintain and sufficiently build capacity to successfully execute translation to meaningful end.</p>

		<p>Training and professional development opportunities can be especially successful ways of enhancing capacity but also for creating opportunities for interdisciplinary growth at a hub as well as across the CTSA Program. Examples of this include: a) Training in information science and informatics is critical for anyone impacted or directly using standards/data interoperability; b) Training in business and management for research professionals is an investment that can accelerate the rate at which early-stage investigators establish their lab and learn the ropes of such critical activities such as developing a budget, short- and long-range planning, hiring/firing, time management, conflict resolution, etc; c) Training in project management and use of modern communication strategies to support cross-disciplinary team science and build the foundation for innovation.</p>
	Encouraging experiential training in the translational science enterprise in non-academic settings	A CTSA-wide coordinated exchange program could be an effective way to support this type of influx of experiential learning into the academic translational community, as well as vice versa - bringing our academic innovation and data creation and research methods to industry. Such an exchange program could support improved partnerships between the CTSA and industry.
	Establishing programs for workforce development for clinical and translational science, including optimal mentoring approaches for junior investigators	<p>One of the major culture changes needed is to start better valuing the diversity of non-traditional contributions that translational science generates for the entire translational workforce. Real translational science is not easily measured, and manuscripts and grant applications are a poor proxy. For this reason, one key opportunity is to have mentors help mentees track their earlier contributions and promote them, using best practices in communication, dissemination, and discoverability. Mentors should consider these types of contributions when they hire people, and when they serve on search committees and T&P committees. CTSA can also help improve T&P criteria to better support credit for these non traditional contributions. Finally, CTSA evaluation cores need to better track these types of contributions from their trainees, and do so in a standardized manner across the network. Current work by the Methods & Processes EC on promotion and tenure language with respect to team-based work shows that there is increasing appreciation and support for researchers to include this facet in their formal promotion, as has been successfully championed by NUCATS for the Northwestern University Team Scientist Faculty Track, for example. Clearly establishing and defining open and inclusive promotion guidelines (e.g., encouraging non-traditional outputs to be included in the formal materials and guidance on how to highlight these accomplishments most clearly for reviewers. Providing a forum for ongoing discussion and by hubs and their academic leadership on how this topic can be advanced by CTSA hubs can help to create and grow a community of practice around this key aspect of credit, recognition, and promotion, essential for the future of this field and biomedicine in general.</p>
Community Engagement, Health Disparities, and Dissemination	Fostering the role of the CTSA in bringing research leading to better health to local communities through implementation and delivery research, including approaches for bringing greater inclusivity into research and training	<p>Need to build/support for the non-academic regional healthcare settings more; have more regional partnerships.</p> <p>Need to find ways to share implementation successes, failures, and best practices and collaborate on those across hubs</p> <p>We should invest in work to understand and optimize best practices in dissemination of research to colleagues and to the public as well as invest in opportunities that can be possible through improvements in discoverability of research results, data, and complementing study materials.</p> <p>Leverage existing structures in communities that are being tapped for research related activities. An example of this is the role that academic and public libraries play with research efforts like All of Us, research readiness initiatives, and health equity programs.</p>
	Improving the protection of human subjects in ways that simultaneously improve oversight and minimize burden and delays (e.g., central or reciprocal IRB reviews, model consent processes)	We as a community need better understanding and development of national human subjects research standards/infrastructure to support a) making data sharing safe for patients, b) contributions or donations of data to research by patients, and c) the ability of individuals to see their data donated in context of other data, research, and outcomes. It is still too difficult for individuals to benefit from donating their data. Based on studies of bias in the use of health information, more investigation is needed to understand how data can possibly exacerbate health disparities. We recommend a cross-CTSA, cross EC working group perform a landscape analysis across CTSA and prioritize the development of CTSA-wide infrastructure to support improved patient control of their data and incentives for their participation.
Additional Considerations	Establishing priorities for shared activities across the CTSA Program hubs as well as methods to incorporate newly-emerging, high-priority activities into the Program	One of the major challenges in supporting shared activities across the CTSA program is that the current funding model actually has some incentives not to collaborate or share activities. The current FOA reads that

		<p>hubs should address how they are working on the “development, demonstration, and dissemination of informatics and IT innovations that accelerate both the science and operations of clinical translation”. This basically suggests that rather than a focus on implementation, maturation, and collaboration on tools and algorithms, for example, it will increase the chances for funding if each CTSA develops their own new innovations. There is simply no financial incentive to mature resources developed at another institution. Further, the fact that CTSA can lose their funding makes it very challenging for them to maintain the buy-in and partnerships they need at their institutions in order to be maximally successful at implementation of CTSA programs. Another challenge is the fact that the data assets are not managed in the same way, or institutionally supported to the same degree across CTSA hubs. If we have a hope to become a research analytics network, we need to have standards for managing and sharing clinical data for research, and the ability to ensure their funding and sustainability. Such capabilities should be a review criteria, which would incentivize institutions to value such resources more.</p>
	Developing and assessing the structure and impact of pilot project programs	<p>We need to change incentive structures within the pilot programs to move from promoting only new innovations to reusing and maturing existing ones by supporting collaborations across the translational ecosystem. Translation is just as much about implementation in the real world as it is about new innovations. Finally, we should support more multi-institutional pilot awards and those that are cross-sector, such as with policy experts, industry, etc.</p>
	Measuring impact of the CTSA Program	<p>We need more implementation measures of changed care improving patients' lives or otherwise the operations of healthcare. We also need more measures that illustrate how shared infrastructure, data sharing, or data interoperability have influenced translation and affected peoples lives. None of these measures should be limited to impact only in the CTSA or in the US - we are responsible for improving the lives of all patients. Finally, we should measure how we work together across sectors better - what does our translational collaboration look like, what effects and outcomes does it have, and how can we reveal patterns that predict success?</p>
	Programmatic goals	<p>One fundamental and critical primary goal of the CTSA is to become a distributed data network. Since the USA does not have centralized single-payer system, we are at a huge disadvantage for being able to learn en masse from our clinical data assets. These data sit siloed within each CTSA, in different data structures, with different governance models, containing different data modalities, and with different longitudinal capacities. Starting with regional aggregation or small networks of CTSA hubs makes sense, but these regional efforts must not diverge into N different network models and data structures. Coordinating a shared data model for federated query will be at the heart of making CTSA function as a network. The ACT initiative is a good start, but CTSA needs to make a commitment toward a preferred clinical data structure, ideally leveraging clinical data standards such as FHIR. We also need to better reduce the divide between EHR data and clinical research data. Research standards such as CDISC, BRIDG, caDSR/CDEs, etc, must be made interoperable with FHIR. FHIR must be made interoperable with the other clinical EHR standards such as PCORnet, OMOP, etc, and with basic research standards such as Biolink-model and OBO ontologies.</p> <p>More effort should be made to employ a mentorship model to encourage new voices to be able to take on leadership positions in CTSA program activities, committees, etc. Supports capacity building and helps ensure that we are hearing from a wide range of perspectives as we champion the goals of the CTSA Program more broadly. Further, we need to somehow incentivize institutional leadership and authority for CTSA leaders (for the PIs and the core leads) to aid better integration of the CTSA network philosophy into the individual institution for best decision making towards these ends.</p>
Other		<p>We need better methods and platforms for sharing implementation successes, failures, and best practices across the CTSA hubs for all activities; the coordinating centers should be able to help with this.</p> <p>The current FOA and review process could do with some revision. The fact that CTSA spend ~1 year writing, only to lose funding, even though >80% proposals are funded, suggests that change is needed. We recommend a more graded funding strategy, where the applications must meet specific criteria (success metrics, populations served, resource poor environments considerations, etc.) to determine the level of funding, rather than funding yes/no. The revInclude a greater diversity of expertise on the reviews (e.g. more non-PI level translational scientists).</p>

